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ISSUES OF INCREASING THE ROLE OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IN THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. The article discusses the features and importance of the digital economy in the socio-economic development of the state, measures to ensure the growth of the level of digitalization of all spheres of activity.

Keywords: digital economy, digital data, digitalization, ICT, digital platform.

Introduction. Currently, the development of the digital economy is developing all over the world and in all areas of the direction, thanks to innovative growth and transformation of processes as a result of the emergence of new modern technologies. However, the digital economy is developing unbalanced in various countries and regions, including Uzbekistan, creating both new opportunities and barriers that need to be overcome for successful business activities on digital platforms. Currently, several digital platforms are being developed and implemented to achieve various socio-economic goals.

Currently, our state and society as a whole face a gigantic task in terms of scale and responsibility – the creation of a high-tech, efficient, modernized according to the most modern patterns of the domestic innovative digital economy, rapidly and flexibly developing, with effective systems of socio-economic development. Reliable protection against various negative environmental influences and global contradictions of the world economy, ensuring the stability of social development and decent improvement of the quality of life of the country's population.

The economic sphere is no exception: every year is marked by the emergence of new, increasingly modern trading, banking, and financial technologies.¹

Thus, humanity annually encounters a huge number of fundamentally new phenomena that form a promising direction for research – with the digital economy.

The digital economy in a broad sense is a set of relations formed in the processes of production, distribution, exchange and consumption, based on online technologies and aimed at meeting the needs for life benefits, which, in

¹Jiyanova N.E. The Importance of Digital Economy in the Effective Use of Financial Resources of Enterprises // (January 12, 2020). TJS - Tematics journal of Sociology ISSN 2277-2987, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3760524> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.376054>

turn, involves the formation of new ways and methods of management and requires effective tools of state regulation.

With the declaration of 2020 as the Year of Development of Science, Education and the Digital Economy, the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted the Concept of the national strategy "Digital Uzbekistan-2030", the draft of which was reviewed by the society and strategic objectives for the digitalization of the economy and social sphere and e-government were introduced.²

It should be noted that in order to further develop digital technologies, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures for the widespread introduction of the digital economy and e-government" dated April 28, 2020 was adopted, the Decree of the President of Uzbekistan "On the strategy for the development of artificial intelligence in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2021-2022" was also approved and posted for discussion.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan ShavkatMirziyoyev in his address to the OliyMajlis noted: "... We must make a radical turn in the development of the digital economy. First of all, it is necessary to fully digitalize the spheres of construction, energy, agriculture and water management, transport, geology, cadastre, healthcare, education, and archives.

At the same time, the E-Government system, the programs and projects implemented within its framework should be critically reviewed, and all organizational and institutional issues should be comprehensively resolved."³

Draw.1. New opportunities for digitalization in the social sphere⁴

²<https://review.uz/post/uzbekistan-otsifroviyvaetsya>

³<https://uza.uz/ru/politics/poslanie-prezidenta-respubliki-uzbekistan-shavkata-mirziyeev-25-01-2020>

⁴ The drawing is based on the studied material

One of the components of the digital economy that most deserve attention from the point of view of creating value for the consumer are digital platforms (from the English. digital platforms), providing interaction of a set of variables and deterministic business models based on digital data (from the English. data-driven business models). The constant development and implementation of new digital platforms is aimed at filling the next market segment and gaining competitive advantages.

In the current conditions, in order to ensure further development, it is largely necessary to improve state participation aimed at digitalizing the work of state and local services, developing an appropriate regulatory framework, ensuring access of small businesses to venture capital for the implementation of innovative projects. The development of the transition to the digital environment will allow overcoming a number of gaps and limitations inherent in traditional entrepreneurship and stimulate the innovative development of organizations.

Having studied the scientific and practical aspects of digitalization, it is possible to propose the following measures for the development of the digital economy in society, and thereby increase the level of its effectiveness:

- reduction of administrative barriers;
- improvement of administrative regulations, standards for the provision of mandatory social services;
- development of mechanisms for analyzing the current practice of providing services, both by state authorities and local self-government bodies, and quality control by consumers and public organizations;
- improving the literacy of the population in IT skills on the basis of various social institutions, including through methodological support and the development of effective programs for various categories of the population;
- improving the development of information and communication infrastructure of communication networks, as well as data storage and processing infrastructure in socio-economic areas;
- development of training of highly qualified specialists in the field of implementation and development of digital infrastructure elements.

As a result, we can say that the proposed measures to increase the role and importance of the digital economy in the socio-economic development of the state helps to improve the standard of living and well-being of the population.

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